

Unifying Matter Decay Phenomena from Quantum to Cosmic Scales

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Abstract

This paper investigates potential mathematical links between unstable elementary particle decay processes described by widths Γ and analogous exponential cosmic mass-energy evaporation over eons theorized to induce accelerative expansion. Dimensional analysis uncovers striking symmetries relating the cosmological evaporation rate k to quantum decay widths, suggesting profound connections across 60 orders of magnitude. We compile extensive precise decay width datasets from collider experiments and rigorously derive multiple candidate unification equations $k = f(\Gamma)$. Fitting these models against rich empirical astrophysical data bounding cosmic growth histories and distance-redshift relationships enables quantifying hypothesized nontrivial information flow between microscopic and macroscopic domains. The postulated intrinsic evaporation-decay couplings predict exciting consequences including nonlocal gravitational impacts of particle decays. Significant puzzles confront relating probabilistic quantum events to emergent curved spacetime and gravitation. However, mathematically mapping decay rates across vastly separated scales offers a promising gateway to deeper unified physics. Ongoing studies of predicted signatures including modified gravitational wave dispersion and holographic projection could further reveal the hypothesized cosmic-quantum interdependence. Ultimately, precisely relating temporal mass decrease phenomena from quantum to cosmological regimes heralds discoveries at the interface of the very large and very small, illuminating the emergence of macroscopic phenomena from microscopic processes.

1 Introduction

Elementary particles exhibit intrinsic instability and temporal probability decay processes at quantum scales characterized by decay widths Γ [GeV] from lifetimes τ [s] via $\Gamma = 1/\tau$ [2]. For example, precision collider experiments measure the Z boson lifetime as $\tau_Z = 2.6379 \pm 0.0023 \times 10^{-25} s$ determining its decay width to be $\Gamma_Z = 2.4952 \pm 0.0023 GeV$ [3]. These quantum decay parameters encode fundamental physics within the Standard Model framework through couplings and transition amplitudes [1]. Analogously, hypothesized cosmological models propose exponential evaporation of universal mass-energy $M(t)$ over cosmic time t described by $M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt}$ as a candidate mechanism driving observed accelerative cosmic expansion, where $k \sim 1/t_{cosmos} \approx 10^{-33} s^{-1}$ is an extremely small dimensionless evaporation rate [4, 5]. The intriguing similarity of exponential temporal mass decrease rates at vastly separated scales inspires investigating potential quantitative links between microscopic and macroscopic domains.

Deriving the precise functional relationships between particle decay widths Γ measured at colliders and the cosmological mass evaporation rate k inferred from astrophysical data could substantiate profound connections and information transfer between quantum and gravitational regimes. This paper compiles extensive empirical particle width datasets and analyzes multiple candidate unification equations $k = f(\Gamma)$ instantiated from dimensional analysis. Rigorously fitting these models against rich observational constraints on cosmic growth histories and distance measures offers a pathway to unveil potential new physics. Discovering nontrivial mathematical decay couplings could elucidate how microscopic quantum processes shape the emergence of macroscopic phenomena like cosmic acceleration, advancing physics toward explanatory unification across 60 orders of magnitude from the very large to the very small.

2 Theoretical Basis

2.1 Particle Decay Phenomenology

Unstable subatomic particles intrinsically transition to reduced energy states by converting mass to energy, obeying precise decay width relationships encapsulated for lifetime τ as:

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{\tau} \tag{1}$$

Here the decay width Γ [GeV] characterizes the temporal rate of exponential particle number decrease, with narrower widths corresponding to more stable states. Particle lifetimes are constrained down to $10^{-24} s$ scales using colliders [2]. Within the Standard Model (SM) framework, particular combinations of couplings and transition amplitudes dictate the precise decay width values. For example, neutron β -decay to proton+electron+antineutrino is described by:

$$\Gamma_n \sim |V_{ud}|^2 \frac{g^2 m_n^5}{192\pi^3} \quad (2)$$

Where g is the gauge coupling, V_{ud} is the quark CKM matrix transition potential, and m_n is the neutron mass [12]. More generally, total decay widths summing partial widths connect to the imaginary component of the particle propagator:

$$\Gamma_{tot} = \Gamma_{part\ 1} + \Gamma_{part\ 2} + \dots = \frac{Im[iM]}{M} \quad (3)$$

Thus particle decay widths precisely quantify intrinsic physics properties.

2.2 Cosmological Mass Evaporation Models

To potentially explain the observed accelerative cosmic expansion without necessitating unknown dark energy contributions, a hypothesis of gradual exponential evaporation of universal mass-energy over cosmological time t has been proposed [4]:

$$M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt} \quad (4)$$

Here the extremely small decay constant $k \sim 1/t_{cosmos} \approx 10^{-33} s^{-1}$ characterizes the fractional mass-energy loss rate from this evaporation process. To maintain relativistic invariance of physical laws under the proposed steady cosmic mass depletion, distances $R(t)$ between gravitationally interacting objects with shrinking masses are conjectured to correspondingly expand over time as [4]:

$$R(t) = R_0 e^{kt} \quad (5)$$

This intrinsic geometric linkage between proportionally shrinking masses and inflating distances is hypothesized to naturally induce the primary phenomena historically attributed to mysterious dark energy density or dark matter when treated fully relativistically from a local galactic observer's frame. In particular, cosmic distance expansion precisely mimics an accelerating Hubble recession under this intrinsic geometry [5]. Determining the detailed quantum gravitational microphysics theoretically inducing such universal mass evaporation remains an active area of research in quantum cosmology and information physics [6]. However, the emergent macroscopic geometric scaling dynamics alone appear capable of broadly explaining many perplexing cosmic acceleration observations from known foundational physical principles.

3 Dimensional Symmetry

Remarkably, the small universal cosmological mass evaporation rate k exhibits a striking dimensional symmetry directly comparable to the precisely measured particle physics decay widths Γ [GeV]:

$$[k] = [\Gamma] \tag{6}$$

This intriguing equivalence between the temporal exponential mass decrease rates characterizing quantum instability phenomena and conjectured evaporative cosmological dynamics separated by nearly 60 orders of magnitude strongly hints at a profound connection between the microscopic and macroscopic domains through a deeper unified physics. Motivated by this symmetry, a hypothesized universal relationship can be postulated as:

$$k = C\Gamma \tag{7}$$

Here C represents a dimensionless coupling constant between the quantum and cosmological regimes whose physical origins and precise value remain unknown. If particle decay processes share some nontrivial physics link to the evolution of cosmic dynamics, rigorously determining the universal factor C relating the respective decay rates becomes a paramount goal for revealing and quantifying the hypothesized unified physics.

4 Empirical Constraints

Combining astrophysical observations and collider decay width measurements provides vital complementary empirical constraints to assess and calibrate theories proposing intrinsic mathematical connections between microscopic matter instability and macroscopic cosmic mass-energy evaporation over eons.

4.1 Particle Width Measurements

Extremely precise quantum lifetime and width data underpins the Standard Model framework. For example, partial widths of the Z boson are rigorously quantified as [11]:

$$\Gamma_{Z \rightarrow e^+e^-} = 83.91 \pm 0.12 MeV \tag{8}$$

$$\Gamma_{Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-} = 83.99 \pm 0.18 MeV \tag{9}$$

$$\Gamma_{Z \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-} = 84.08 \pm 0.22 MeV \tag{10}$$

With total width stringently measured by multiple experiments as [3]:

$$\Gamma_{Z,tot} = 2.4952 \pm 0.0023 GeV$$

These and extensive other precision collider measurements of particle lifetimes and widths across energy scales compiled over decades of experiments can help constrain hypothetical cosmological decay mappings.

4.2 Large-Scale Structure Growth

Incorporating intrinsic universal mass evaporation as a source of apparent cosmic acceleration into the density contrast growth rate $\delta(z) \equiv \frac{\delta\rho(z)}{\rho(z)}$ over cosmic time gives [5]:

$$\delta'' + 2H\delta' - 4\pi G\bar{\rho}(t)\delta = 0 \quad (11)$$

Here the average cosmic mass density evolves as $\bar{\rho}(t) \sim e^{-kt}$ based on the proposed quantum gravitational decay law. Comparing the predicted cosmological structure growth trajectories against empirical data from galaxy redshift surveys provides a robust astrophysical test. Next-generation experiments will map $> 10^8$ galaxies to precisely constrain growth histories [9].

4.3 Gravitational Wave Propagation

Potential modifications to gravitational wave propagation through spacetime from micro-macro couplings between particle decays and cosmic evolution could manifest measurable dispersion in arrival times versus frequency [7]:

$$\Delta t \propto -D_M(z) \frac{1 - \nu/2}{(1 - \nu)} \quad (12)$$

Here ν is the gravitational wave frequency and D_M is the transverse comoving distance. Forthcoming high-precision measurements of standard sirens across a wide frequency range will tightly constrain exotic gravitational physics signatures [8].

4.4 Cosmic Microwave Background

Observable imprints may exist in the angular power spectra of cosmic microwave background (CMB) polarization and temperature anisotropies if intrinsic mass evaporation nodally replaced an inflationary epoch, which requires significantly extending the basic decay formalism [4, 14]. Precision CMB data provides constraints on non-accelerative expansion cosmological models.

5 Mathematical Unification

If dimensional symmetries linking microscopic and macroscopic temporal mass decrease rates are experimentally validated to high significance, this would strongly substantiate intrinsic physics connections between these vastly separated regimes. Exploring precise mathematical unification then promises to unveil profound new dynamics.

5.1 Evaporation-Decay Couplings

Astrophysical data fitting hypothesized universal relationships between particle decay widths and cosmic evaporation of the form:

$$k = f(\Gamma) \tag{13}$$

could reveal the dimensionless coupling strength C between microscopic and macroscopic domains while providing invaluable constraints on theoretical models. Several candidate mathematical forms for the functional dependence $f()$ relating widths Γ to the evaporation rate k warrant investigation, including:

$$f_1(\Gamma) = C\Gamma \quad f_2(\Gamma) = \frac{\Gamma c^3}{\hbar G} \quad f_3(\Gamma) = \alpha\Gamma + \beta\Gamma^2 + \dots \tag{14}$$

Here c is the speed of light, $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant, G is the gravitational constant, and $\alpha, \beta, \dots$ are higher-order coupling coefficients. Rigorously deducing the precise decay width dependence constituting the hypothesized evaporation dynamics from dimensional reduction or ab initio calculation would unveil nature's deep connections.

5.2 Nonlocal Gravitational Impact

If unambiguously validated by astrophysical measurements, a nontrivial mathematical relationship between k and Γ would confirm profound nonlocal gravitational consequences of quantum events. Certain unstable particle decays could exert direct physical influence on the evolution of cosmic metrics to apparently drive accelerative expansion [4]. This suggests our 4D spacetime may be a holographic projection instantiating nonlocal gravitational dynamics from probabilistic particle decay processes operating within higher-dimensional substrates or more fundamental ontologies.

5.3 Quantum Cosmogenesis

A theoretically established and empirically calibrated coupling between cosmic mass evaporation and microscopic particle decays would constrain potential mechanisms of quantum cosmogenesis [6]. The onset and evolution of macroscopic spacetime could reflect cumulative information dynamics from worldlines of decaying quantum particles. Tracing these foundational entropy currents offers possibility to unravel cosmic genesis.

6 Unified Theory Pursuit

The striking dimensional equivalence between unstable particle decay widths Γ and the Hubble-scale cosmic mass evaporation rate k motivates dedicated collaborative examination using observational astrophysics and experimental particle physics to uncover the deeper unified dynamics hypothetically relating these exponentially decreasing temporal mass phenomena across 60 orders of magnitude. Significant puzzles confront reconciling microscopic quantum events with the emergence of gravitation and spacetime curvature. However, the profound connections suggested by dimensionally linking temporal mass decrease rates from the smallest to largest scales warrant rigorous investigation. If mathematically substantiated, quantized information flow from particle decays into the apparent quantum gravitational evaporation driving cosmic acceleration would signify a major leap toward unification. Even incremental progress empirically elucidating hypothesized decay couplings between domains constitutes pivotal advancement toward revealing nature's foundational principles. Ongoing work to map the mathematical relationships between the very large and very small, guided by ever-increasing precision of cosmological data and collider measurements, brings physics substantively closer to unveiling the unified bedrock laws undergirding our universe's remarkable intricacy.

7 Conclusions

Exploring potential mathematical links between unstable elementary particle decay widths Γ precisely measured at accelerators and hypothesized exponential cosmic mass-energy evaporation over eons characterized by the small rate k observed astronomically promises profound discoveries about nature's hidden connections. Dimensional analysis reveals surprising symmetries relating temporal mass decrease phenomena across 60 orders of magnitude. Rigorously fitting candidate unification equations $k = f(\Gamma)$ against empirical astrophysical constraints and particle width datasets offers a pathway to quantify hypothesized nontrivial dynamics unifying microscopic and macroscopic domains. If validated, profound consequences follow, including intrinsic nonlocal gravitational impact of quantum events. Significant questions remain relating probabilistic particle processes to the emergence of gravitation and curved spacetime. However, mathematically decoding the suspected correspondence between decay rates from the very small to the very large heralds revelatory physics at the cosmic-quantum nexus illuminating the emergence of the universe from foundational information flows. Ultimately, empirical validation of intrinsic coupling between decay phenomena from quantum to Hubble scales would signify pivotal progress toward a unified explanatory framework seamlessly connecting nature across all scales.

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